

Fig S1. Examples of visual evidence of *N. barbata* disease, taken with permission from Tacey et al. 2023. White arrows signify fungal lesions. (a) shows an individual with no visual signs of disease. (b), (c), (e) and (f) are diseased males while (d) is a diseased female. Permission to use this figure from the published paper has been granted by the original author.

Table S1. Model output showing effect of fixed covariates on infection status for the Base model. Effect size shows the direction and magnitude of the effect the covariate has on an individual’s infection susceptibility, expressed on the scale of standard deviation. For discrete covariates (Sex and Age Class) effect size represent the difference in means between the two classes contained in the covariates (Sex – males and females; Age Class – juveniles and adults). For all other covariates, the effect size represents the slope of the regression of the respective variable on infection status. Credible Intervals (CI) show the lower 2.5% and upper 97.5% quantile for each covariate. In **bold** are the estimates where CI does not include zero, indicative of a significant effect.

<i>Fixed Effect</i>	<i>Effect Size</i>	<i>Credible Intervals (2.5%, 9.75%)</i>
<i>Sex (Male)</i>	1.043	0.371, 1.766
<i>Time in Population (days)</i>	1.000	0.644, 1.419
<i>Age Class (Discrete: Juvenile)</i>	-1.401	-2.164, -0.672
<i>Disease Interactions</i>	-0.216	-0.494, 0.059
<i>Diseased Conspecific density per m²</i>	1.183	0.838, 1.548
<i>Season 2015-16</i>	-3.151	-5.196, -1.158
<i>Season 2016-17</i>	-1.484	-3.065, 0.093
<i>Season 2017-18</i>	0.687	-0.748, 2.155
<i>Season 2018-19</i>	2.533	1.100, 4.048
<i>Season 2019-20</i>	3.116	1.590, 4.755
<i>Season 2020-21</i>	4.481	2.945, 6.189
<i>Season 2021-22</i>	6.051	4.389, 7.939
<i>Season 2022-23</i>	5.993	4.265, 7.969

Table S2. Model output showing effect of fixed covariates on infection status for the tSPDE model. Effect size shows the direction and magnitude of the effect the covariate has on an individual’s infection susceptibility, expressed on the scale of standard deviation. For discrete covariates (Sex and Age Class) effect size represent the difference in means between the two classes contained in the covariates (Sex – males and females; Age Class – juveniles and adults). For all other covariates, the effect size represents the slope of the regression of the respective variable on infection status. Credible Intervals (CI) show the lower 2.5% and upper 97.5% quantile for each covariate. In **bold** are the estimates where CI does not include zero, indicative of a significant effect.

<i>Fixed Effect</i>	<i>Effect Size</i>	<i>Credible Intervals (2.5%, 9.75%)</i>
<i>Sex (Male)</i>	1.050	0.373, 1.778
<i>Time in Population (days)</i>	1.009	0.650, 1.426
<i>Age Class (Discrete: Juvenile)</i>	-1.409	-2.177, -0.675
<i>Disease Interactions</i>	-0.221	-0.503, 0.057
<i>Diseased Conspecific density per m²</i>	1.196	0.846, 1.567
<i>Season 2015-16</i>	-3.175	-5.247, -1.157
<i>Season 2016-17</i>	-1.496	-3.098, 0.100
<i>Season 2017-18</i>	0.692	-0.761, 2.179
<i>Season 2018-19</i>	2.558	1.106, 4.092
<i>Season 2019-20</i>	3.144	1.600, 4.798
<i>Season 2020-21</i>	4.528	2.970, 6.247
<i>Season 2021-22</i>	6.106	4.421, 7.996
<i>Season 2022-23</i>	6.048	4.296, 8.022